

NEWSLETTER

COMPAS_sCO₂

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Issue : III

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. 958418

Project Team: 12 participants from 7 countries

Research focus: New particles, metal alloys and heat exchanger

Duration: 1 November 2020 – 31 October 2024

Status of Implementation

Eighteen months after the kick-off meeting that took place virtually on November 2nd, 2020, significant results, deliverables, milestones have been achieved. All public deliverables and main activities are freely accessible through the project's website: <https://www.compassco2.eu/>. The section below summarizes the status of project activities by work package.

WP1 – MATERIALS OPERATION CONDITIONS AND THEIR FEASIBILITY STUDIES

WP1 reinvestigated both low- and high-pressure heat exchanger (HEX) designs. An in-depth and thorough thermomechanical stress analysis was performed within the framework of the basic HEX engineering. This additional work confirmed the list of the preselected materials and emphasizes no major impacts on any other WPs of the project. Nonetheless, this led to submit revised versions of both deliverables D1.2 and D1.3 presenting the new low- and high-pressure HEX configurations and their associated design parameters.

Figure 1: Isometric view of the particle-sCO₂ HEX

WP2 – DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF PARTICLES

Further characterization and optimization activities of the different particle types were undertaken in WP2. The two novel particle types (Figure 2) which were specifically developed for solar thermal applications by Saint-Gobain were sent out to the partners. They have been tested for their mechanical properties like softening temperature, hardness, sphericity, density and heat capacity.

Furthermore their optical properties like solar absorptance and thermal emittance have been evaluated and it could be shown that these novel particles are performing very well regarding the initially set target values. For many parameters they can even be regarded as superior than state-of-the-art particles. In the meantime, the surface treatment procedures are being optimized by variations of e.g. the coating

Figure 2: Microscope images of two novel developed particle types: generations 3 of granulated particles and generation 2 of fused particles. Credit: Nassira Benameur, Saint-Gobain.

WP3 - DEVELOPMENT OF METALS

WP 3 seeks increased durability of CSP heat exchanger materials. This has started from state-of-the-art commercial nickel superalloys and austenitic steels, as well as novel Cr alloys - selected for their high melting point, low price and exceptional oxidation resistance. Work is focussed on their strength, erosion resistance, toughness, and oxidation/corrosion under air/supercritical-CO₂.

The state-of-the-art materials have been selected, procured, and prepared for

characterisation and mechanical tests that are underway in CIEMAT (Spain) and OCAS (Belgium). The development of Cr-NiAl alloys is underway at University of Birmingham (U.K.), in parallel to Cr-Si based alloys in DECHEMA (Germany). The alloys have been manufactured by arc melting, see figure below. Their microstructures have been studied using advanced characterization tools including electron microscopy and atom probe tomography. Their corrosion resistance is being studied in DECHEMA (Germany).

Figure 3: Kan Ma working on a mini arc-melter to manufacture Cr alloys at UoB; (right-up) as-cast Cr-NiAl alloy ingot; (right-down) Cr-NiAl sample mounted in bakelite and polished ready for electron microscope observations

WP4 - EVALUATION AND MODELING OF METAL/MEDIUM INTERACTION

In WP4 all experimental instruments are arranged and the tests are ongoing. The sets of creep data are being acquired at a test temperature of 700°C in both air and CO₂ atmospheres for varying loads for both interrupted and rupture creep tests. Strain

vs. time for both IN740 and SANICRO25 in air are shown below (courtesy of CIEMAT). Comparisons will be made across the state-of-the-art materials with thorough analysis including fractography and microstructural characterization.

Figure 4: Strain vs. time for both IN740 and SANICRO25 in air

WP5 – TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION

WP5 is devoted to the development and verification of the particle/sCO₂ HEX and the surrounding systems such as particle transportation system. The cold test experimental setup is being completed (Figure 5, left) and will allow to observe the particle flow between various configurations of the tube banks in order to identify the optimal particle flow distribution. To assess the particle flow, it will be recorded on video and postprocessed with PIV algorithm. To obtain better image contrast, the project

partners from CIEMAT provided coloured particles (Figure 5, right). Furthermore, the pneumatic particle transportation system will be validated within the cold test.

Another ongoing parallel activity is the detail design of the particle heating system, which fabrications is about to begin. The heater will heat the particles up 900°C. Thus, the verification of the particle/sCO₂ HEX under the real conditions will be enabled.

Figure 5: Cold test experimental setup (left), Particles SB 30/50 with two colour variation will be used to get better contrast for PIV tracking (right)

Communication & dissemination activities

COMPASsCO₂ Poster

The [COMPASsCO₂ poster](#) gives a general overview of the COMPASsCO₂ project, including addressed challenges, research focus (new particles and new metals

alloys for the particle/sCO₂ heat exchanger and their validation) as well as stakeholders engagement /dissemination and the composition of the consortium.

Figure 6: COMPASsCO₂ Poster

Informative paper – Development and testing of new particle for high-temperature concentrating solar receivers: state of the art and innovation brought by COMPASsCO₂.

This [paper](#) released on March 31st is a first of a series of informative papers aiming at disseminating the main achievements of COMPASsCO₂ project to a wide audience, in order to increase awareness on sustainable energy technologies and highlight the efforts of both research and

industry for the transition to a carbon neutral energy mix in Europe. It summarises the activities conducted in the first 18 months of implementation (November 2020 – April 2022), and the main accomplishments, with a specific focus on the development and testing of novel materials.

Figure 7: First Informative Paper

Meetings

Third Project Meeting – The 3rd project meeting took place on February 4th, 2022. The meeting was organized virtually. It gathered the project's participants who discussed the overall progress, on-going activities, challenges, and next steps.

Technical Committee Meeting – The TCM was held also on February 4th, 2022 to further discuss the main challenges, internal coordination among the different WPs and any risks and mitigation measures.

First Review Meeting - The 1st review meeting took place on April 7th 2022. The

meeting was organized in hybrid format (at John Cockerill HQ in Seraing, Belgium and online). In addition to project participants, the European Commission Project Officer and an external reviewer attended in order to assess the work conducted during the first 18 months of implementation and provide recommendations for the next phase.

Dedicated WP Meetings – Several dedicated WP meetings were organized to discuss the technical aspects of the project with involved partners.

Figure 8: Project participants attending the First Review Meeting, physically, at John Cockerill HQ, Seraing, Belgium and online

Joint activities with Similar Project

A number of joint communication and dissemination activities are envisaged with other similar projects, including:

CARBOSOLA

CO2OLHEAT

DESOLINATION

SCARABEUS

sCO2-Efekt

sCO2-4-NPP

ASTEP

MOSAIC

SFERA III

NEXTOWER

Within the framework of joint communication and dissemination activities with similar projects, a series of webinars are being envisaged on different topics. The first webinar will cover a general introduction on sCO₂-related projects, and is scheduled for September 2022.

All communication and dissemination activities will be announced through the different projects' websites.

How to get involved in COMPASsCO₂ activities

Become a member of the project's stakeholders' network

Whether you want to learn more about specific WP activities, collaborate with the consortium or act as an external expert, kindly contact us at contact@compassco2.eu. We will keep you updated about project activities, invite you to attend the project's public events and ask your feedback on the progress and main outcomes of the project.

Check our website and follow us on social media networks

LinkedIn

<https://www.compassco2.eu/>

THANK YOU

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

Contact us: contact@compassco2.eu

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